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A Dynamic Spring Element Model for the Prediction of Longitudinal Failure of Polymer Composites

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Longitudinal tensile failure of polymer composites

Failure sequence:

1. Weaker fibres fail at lower strains (flaw dominated process)
2. Load from the broken fibre is transferred into the intact ones by the matrix
3. Stress concentration and flaws lead to the breakage of more fibres
4. Interaction of fibre breaks lead to the formation of clusters of broken fibres
5. A cluster of broken fibres reaches a critical size and propagates unstably
6. Unstable crack propagation leads to the failure of the material

Swolfs, Y. et al., 2015. Composites part A

Modelling approaches

3D Micromechanical FEM

- Real 3D model
- Detailed material models and full characterization of all physical phenomena
- Computationally expensive
- Low number of fibres represented in the RVE

Spring Element Model (SEM)

- Simplified 1D model with 3D microscopic representation
- Fibre fracture and shear stress redistribution is considered
- Computationally efficient
- Large RVEs can be simulated even using real fibre distributions

Static Spring Element model

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Spring Element Model (SEM)

Shear load at r : $f_m(r) = GA_m(r) \frac{du}{dr}$ Equilibrium: $\frac{d}{dr} \left(GA_m(r) \frac{du}{dr} \right) = 0$

Stiffness matrix of the matrix elements: $\mathbf{K}_m = \frac{G \left(A_m^{(2)} - A_m^{(1)} \right)}{d \ln \left(A_m^{(2)} / A_m^{(1)} \right)} \begin{bmatrix} 1 & -1 \\ -1 & 1 \end{bmatrix}$

Stiffness matrix of the fibre elements: $\mathbf{K}_f^e = \frac{A_f^e E^e}{lz} \begin{bmatrix} 1 & -1 \\ -1 & 1 \end{bmatrix}$

Virtual work: $\delta \mathbf{u}^T \left[\left(\sum_{e=1}^{N_f - N_f^b} \mathbf{K}_f^e + \sum_{e=1}^{N_m - N_m^b} \mathbf{K}_m^e \right) \mathbf{u} \right] = \delta \mathbf{u}^T \mathbf{f}$

Global stiffness matrix

$A_m^{(1)} = \frac{2\pi R_1}{n_1} lz$

$A_m(r) = A_m^{(1)} + \frac{(A_m^{(2)} - A_m^{(1)})}{d} r$

$A_m^{(2)} = \frac{2\pi R_2}{n_2} lz$

Failure modelling

- **Maximum stress criterion for fibre failure**

$$\frac{\sigma_f}{X_T^e} - 1 < 0 \quad \text{if} \quad \sigma_f > 0$$

- **Stochastic fibre strength**

- Weibull $X_e^t = \sigma_0 \left[-\frac{L_0}{L} \ln(1 - R_1) \right]^{1/m}$
- PLAW $X_e^t = \sigma_0 \left[-\left(\frac{L_0}{L} \right)^\alpha \ln(1 - R_1) \right]^{1/m}$
- WOW $X_f^e = \left(\frac{L_0}{L} \right)^{1/\rho'} \sigma_0 (-\ln(1 - R_1))^{1/\rho'} (-\ln(1 - R_2))^{1/m}$

- **Matrix elastic-perfectly plastic response**
- Sequentially linear analysis,

$$G_{i+1} = \frac{G_i}{\alpha_m}$$

Failure modelling

- **Maximum stress criterion for fibre failure**

$$\frac{\sigma_f}{X_T^e} - 1 < 0 \quad \text{if} \quad \sigma_f > 0$$

- **Stochastic fibre strength**

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Note: Madhukar and Drzal (1991) tested AS4 composites in an EPON 828 matrix and obtained a tensile strength for the composite material of 1890 MPa and a failure strain of 1.45%

Fibre failure and clustering process

- Predicted mean value of the critical cluster size: 12.6 fibres
- T700 (Scott 2011): 14 fibres.

Dynamic Spring Element model

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Dynamic spring element model

- Governing equation

$$\mathbf{M}\ddot{\mathbf{u}} + \mathbf{C}\dot{\mathbf{u}} + \mathbf{K}\mathbf{u} = \mathbf{f}^{\text{ext}}$$

- Mass matrices

$$\mathbf{M}_f^e = A_f^e \rho_f^e l^z \begin{bmatrix} 1/3 & 1/6 \\ 1/6 & 1/3 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\mathbf{M}_m^e = \rho_m d \begin{bmatrix} 1/12 (3A_1 + A_2) & 1/12 (A_1 + A_2) \\ 1/12 (A_1 + A_2) & 1/12 (A_1 + 3A_2) \end{bmatrix}$$

- Diagonal mass matrix via row-sum method

- Rayleigh damping $\mathbf{C} = \alpha\mathbf{M} + \beta\mathbf{K}$

Algorithm 1 Flowchart for explicit time integration.

- 1: Time Update $t_{n+1} = t_n + \Delta t$
 - 2: First Partial nodal velocity update $\dot{\mathbf{u}}_{t+\Delta t/2} = \dot{\mathbf{u}}_t + \frac{\Delta t}{2}\ddot{\mathbf{u}}_t$
 - 3: Enforce velocity boundary conditions
 - 4: Update nodal displacements $\mathbf{u}_{t+\Delta t} = \mathbf{u} + \Delta t\dot{\mathbf{u}}_{t+\Delta t/2}$
 - 5: Compute internal and external forces
 - 6: compute accelerations $\ddot{\mathbf{u}}_{t+\Delta t} = \mathbf{M}^{-1} (\mathbf{f}_{t+\Delta t}^{\text{ext}} - \mathbf{f}_{t+\Delta t}^{\text{int}})$
 - 7: Communicate accelerations to ghost nodes
 - 8: Second Partial nodal velocity update $\dot{\mathbf{u}}_{t+\Delta t} = \dot{\mathbf{u}}_{t+\Delta t/2} + \frac{\Delta t}{2}\ddot{\mathbf{u}}_{t+\Delta t}$
 - 9: Compute kinetic and internal energies
 - 10: Output; if stop criterion not met, go to 1
-

Dynamic fibre break process

The strain energy of the broken fibre is converted into kinetic energy, which creates a stress wave that propagates in the broken fibre and affects the stress concentration on the surrounding intact fibres

Stress concentration after a fibre breaks

- Comparison between SCFs in the static and dynamic cases:
 - Design of experiments with 36 cases
 - 10 simulations with a random fibre distribution

Factor	Level	SCF_{max}^{Din}		SCF_{max}^{Stat}		SCF_{Inc}	
		Avg.	CoV (%)	Avg.	CoV (%)	Avg. (%)	CoV (%)
E_f (GPa)	70	1.206	12.75	1.123	6.61	52.47	55.19
	230	1.257	11.48	1.155	6.22	58.36	31.66
	480	1.289	10.41	1.177	5.69	58.83	27.85
G_m (MPa)	450	1.268	11.12	1.164	6.12	57.70	31.96
	1050	1.232	12.11	1.140	6.49	55.40	44.65
τ^u (MPa)	50	1.129	4.92	1.089	2.86	39.55	37.45
	100	1.192	5.71	1.130	3.93	46.88	10.66
	∞	1.430	4.12	1.235	3.04	83.23	7.35
V_f	0.4	1.291	11.61	1.176	6.40	58.83	30.34
	0.6	1.210	10.74	1.127	5.53	54.27	46.08

- Dynamic SCF is always higher than the static
- Average increase in SCF due to dynamic effects:
 - Elastic matrix $\tau^u = \infty$: 83.23%
 - Elasto-plastic matrix $\tau^u \neq \infty$: 43.21%,
- Other parameters have a low effect on the in the increase of SCF
- The increased maximum SCF will lead to changes in the cluster formation, eventually leading to the formation of more co-planar clusters.

Multiple fibre breaks

Stress-strain behaviour

		X_t		ε_f		Max. cluster		Planar clusters		Break dens.	
		Avg. (MPa)	CV (%)	Avg. (%)	CV (%)	Avg.	CV (%)	Avg. (%)	CV (%)	Avg. (/mm ³)	CV (%)
$\tau^u = 50$ MPa	Static	2946	0.71	2.37	1.26	3.8	28.8	45	22.0	3430	11.0
	Dynamic	2956	1.12	2.32	1.54	5.6	32.4	38	22.8	4362	21.7
$\tau^u = \infty$	Static	3243	0.70	2.56	0.94	28.6	87.8	44	10.8	8873	15.3
	Dynamic	2971	0.77	2.34	1.03	21.4	34.0	40	21.2	7806	15.8

Cluster formation comparison

Elastic matrix $\tau^u = 50$ MPa

Elastic matrix $\tau^u = \infty$

Conclusions

- The simple and efficient computational micromechanical model proposed is able to capture the main mechanics of longitudinal tensile failure composite materials.
- The process of development of clusters of broken fibres leading to localization of fracture is captured by the model, however, there are some key differences with experimental results.
- The dynamic SEM has shown to capture the dynamic effects of fibre failure and the stress wave propagation that leads to increase stress concentration on the surrounding intact fibres.
- The inclusion of dynamic effects had a small effect on the tensile behaviour predicted by the model
- Cluster formation, specially the formation of planar clusters is still underpredicted by the dynamic model